

Termowood

Tewo wood building system

This building system relies on relatively small and light building elements that are plugged and screwed together on the construction site without heavy machinery

Highlights of innovative features

- The Tewo building concept allows for fast assembly and minimal waste on the construction site.
- The simplicity of the system allows for coupling high quality and well insulated buildings with affordable construction costs.
- The Tewo-Flex system is a variant providing flexible and reusable inner walls for office buildings and similar applications.
- Tewo can be used in Building Information and Modelling (BIM) applications.

Tewo constructions are based on structural wall elements consisting of two cross-laminated plywood layers separated by insulation material and joined together with wooden dowels. The elements are prefabricated and arrive ready to be assembled on the construction site. The company is active in Norway, Denmark, the Netherlands, UK and USA.

Company | Ownership of innovation

Factsheet #27 | 2021

Termowood AS
Høversjøvegen 49
2090 Hurdal, Norway

tewo.no

